

Date (UT): 2022-03-11

Observers: Peralta, Bullock,
Huerta Cruz students

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Comments: OSfilter=Open in flat_Fell. Venus in CO flats 2270-2271.
Wrong exposure for bias 1481-1500.

Frame #'s	Object	Expos (s)	Coadds	Dichr	OS	PA (°)	Slit (")	Filter	UT	HA	Comments
			Cycles		Filter				LST	Airmass	
0001-0076	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 76	open	Open	90.000	Mirror	contK	16:33:57 16:37:07	1.80-1.77	Focusing on Venus Filename: img
0077-0151	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 75	open	Open	90.000	Mirror	contK	16:37:38 16:40:45	1.77-1.74	Venus Quick Image Set Filename: img
0152-0176	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 25	open	Open	90.000	Mirror	Bry	16:40:59 16:42:00	1.74-1.73	Venus Quick Image Set Filename: img
0177-0251	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 75	open	PK_50	90.000	Mirror	1.74	16:42:28 16:45:35	1.73-1.70	Venus Quick Image Set Filename: img
0252-0276	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 25	open	PK_50	90.000	Mirror	Fell	16:46:15 16:47:16	1.70-1.69	Venus Quick Image Set Filename: img
0277-0296	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 20	open	Blank	90.000	Mirror	Fell	16:47:39 16:48:27	1.69-1.68	Venus Quick Image Set Filename: dark_0241s_bias
0297-0311	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 15	open	Open	90.000	Mirror	Fell	16:48:39 16:49:15	1.68-1.68	Sky Quick Image Set (100 arcsec N) Filename: flat_Fell
0312-0326	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 15	open	PK_50	90.000	Mirror	1.74	16:49:51 16:50:27	1.67-1.67	Sky Quick Image Set (100 arcsec N) Filename: flat_174
0327-0341	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 15	open	PK_50	90.000	Mirror	Bry	16:50:58 16:51:33	1.66-1.66	Sky Quick Image Set (100 arcsec N) Filename: flat_Bry
0342-0356	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 15	open	PK_50	90.000	Mirror	contK	16:51:45 16:52:20	1.66-1.65	Sky Quick Image Set (100 arcsec N) Filename: flat_contK
0357-0556	Venus (299)	0.1204	1 200	open	Long4	90.000	Mirror	5.1	16:54:10 17:06:07	1.64-1.57	Venus 5.1 Instant Sky Filename: img
0557-0576	Venus (299)	0.1204	1 20	open	Blank	90.000	Mirror	5.1	17:06:40 17:07:50	1.57-1.56	Dark Frames for Venus Filename: dark_012s
0577-0596	Venus (299)	0.1204	1 20	open	Blank	90.000	Mirror	5.1	17:07:53 17:09:02	1.56-1.55	Bias Frames for Venus Filename: bias
0597-0616	Venus (299)	0.1204	1 20	open	Blank	90.000	Mirror	5.1	17:09:05 17:10:15	1.55-1.55	Dark Frames for Venus Filename: dark_012s
0617-0847	Venus (299)	0.2408	2 231	open	Open	90.000	0.5x15	Lp	17:22:31 17:34:16	1.49-1.43	Venus Night LXD_long Scan 1 Filename: img
0848-0892	Venus (299)	0.2408	2 45	open	Open	90.000	0.5x15	Lp	17:36:08 17:38:22	1.43-1.42	Venus Night LXD_long Scan 1 (sky) Filename: img
0893-0965	Venus (299)	0.2408	2 73	open	Open	90.000	0.5x15	Lp	17:41:08 17:44:49	1.41-1.40	Venus Day LXD_long Scan 1 (sky) Filename: img
0966-0977	Venus (299)	0.2408	2 12	open	Open	90.000	0.5x15	Lp	17:45:51 17:46:24	1.39-1.39	Venus Day LXD_long Scan 1 (sky for real) Filename: img
0978-1068	Venus (299)	0.2408	2 91	open	Open	90.000	0.5x60	Lp	17:49:56 17:54:31	1.38-1.37	Venus PRISM Scan 1 Filename: img
1069-1087	Venus (299)	0.2408	2 19	open	Open	90.000	0.5x60	Lp	17:55:23 17:56:18	1.36-1.36	Venus PRISM Scan 1 (sky) Filename: img

IRTF + SpeX (Guider)

PROJECT: 2022A038

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Comments: OSfilter=Open in flat_Fell. Venus in CO flats 2270-2271.
Wrong exposure for bias 1481-1500.

Frame #'s	Object	Expos (s)	Coadds	Dichr	OS	PA (°)	Slit (")	Filter	UT	HA	Comments
			Cycles		Filter				LST	Airmass	
1088-1102	HD_177120	0.9631	1 15	open	Open	90.000	Mirror	contK	18:21:32 18:22:28	1.36-1.36	Reference Star Quick Image Set Filename: img
1103-1117	HD_177120	0.9631	1 15	open	PK_50	90.000	Mirror	1.74	18:22:53 18:23:49	1.36-1.36	Reference Star Quick Image Set Filename: img
1118-1120	HD_177120	29.855	1 3	open	Open	90.000	Mirror	CO+ND2	18:24:14 18:25:22	1.36-1.36	Reference Star Quick Image Set Filename: img
1121-1140	HD_177120	0.2408	1 20	open	Blank	90.000	Mirror	CO+ND2	18:26:24 18:27:13	1.36-1.36	Dark-Bias Frames for Venus Filename: dark_0241s_bias
1141-1150	HD_177120	0.9631	1 10	open	Blank	90.000	Mirror	CO+ND2	18:27:16 18:27:52	1.36-1.36	Dark Frames for Venus and Star Filename: dark_1s
1151-1160	HD_177120	4.8155	1 10	open	Blank	90.000	Mirror	CO+ND2	18:27:56 18:29:19	1.36-1.37	Dark Frames for Venus and Star Filename: dark_5s
1161-1201	HR_7773	0.9631	1 41	open	Long4	90.000	Mirror	5.1	18:33:06 18:36:27	1.22-1.22	Reference Star Quick Image Set Filename: star
1202-1270	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 69	0.9	Open	90.000	Mirror	contK	18:41:49 18:44:43	1.27-1.26	Focusing on Venus Filename: img
1271-1345	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 75	0.9	Open	90.000	Mirror	contK	18:45:18 18:48:27	1.26-1.26	Venus Quick Image Set Filename: img
1346-1370	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 25	0.9	Open	90.000	Mirror	Bry	18:48:41 18:49:43	1.26-1.26	Venus Quick Image Set Filename: img
1371-1445	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 75	0.9	PK_50	90.000	Mirror	1.74	18:50:10 18:53:19	1.26-1.25	Venus Quick Image Set Filename: img
1446-1470	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 25	0.9	PK_50	90.000	Mirror	Fell	18:53:59 18:55:00	1.25-1.25	Venus Quick Image Set Filename: img
1471-1480	Venus (299)	19.984	1 10	0.9	Open	90.000	Mirror	CO+ND2	18:55:24 18:59:02	1.25-1.25	Venus Quick Image Set Filename: img
1481-1500	Venus (299)	19.984	1 20	0.9	Blank	90.000	Mirror	CO+ND2	18:59:42 19:07:21	1.25-1.24	Venus Quick Image Set Filename: dark_0241s_bias
1501-1505	Venus (299)	19.984	1 5	0.9	Open	90.000	Mirror	CO+ND2	19:07:55 19:09:31	1.24-1.24	Sky Quick Image Set (100 arcsec N) Filename: flat_CO
1506-1520	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 15	0.9	Open	90.000	Mirror	Fell	19:10:21 19:10:57	1.24-1.24	Sky Quick Image Set (100 arcsec N) Filename: flat_Fell
1521-1535	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 15	0.9	PK_50	90.000	Mirror	1.74	19:11:33 19:12:08	1.24-1.24	Sky Quick Image Set (100 arcsec N) Filename: flat_174
1536-1550	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 15	0.9	PK_50	90.000	Mirror	Bry	19:12:40 19:13:16	1.24-1.24	Sky Quick Image Set (100 arcsec N) Filename: flat_Bry
1551-1565	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 15	0.9	PK_50	90.000	Mirror	contK	19:13:27 19:14:03	1.24-1.24	Sky Quick Image Set (100 arcsec N) Filename: flat_contK
1566-1580	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 15	0.9	Open	90.000	Mirror	contK	19:15:56 19:16:31	1.24-1.24	Flats (corrected) Filename: flat_contK

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Wrong exposure for bias 1481-1500.

Frame #'s	Object	Expos (s)	Coadds	Dichr	OS	PA (°)	Slit (")	Filter	UT	HA	Comments
			Cycles		Filter				LST	Airmass	
1581-1595	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 15	0.9	Open	90.000	Mirror	Bry	19:16:52 19:17:28	1.24-1.24	Flats (corrected) Filename: flat_Bry
1596-1610	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 15	0.9	Blank	90.000	Mirror	Bry	19:18:06 19:18:41	1.24-1.24	Darks (corrected) Filename: dark_0241
1611-1710	Venus (299)	0.2408	2 100	open	Open	90.000	0.5x60	Lp	19:21:16 19:26:20	1.24-1.24	Venus PRISM Scan 2 Filename: img
1711-1735	Venus (299)	0.2408	2 25	open	Open	90.000	0.5x60	Lp	19:26:41 19:27:55	1.24-1.24	Venus PRISM Scan 2 (sky) Filename: img
1736-1757	Venus (299)	0.2408	2 22	open	Open	90.000	0.5x15	Lp	19:32:24 19:33:29	1.24-1.24	Venus Night LXD_Long Scan 2 (sky) Filename: img
1758-1986	Venus (299)	0.2408	2 229	open	Open	90.000	0.5x15	Lp	19:34:29 19:46:10	1.24-1.24	Venus Night LXD_Long Scan 2 Filename: img
1987-2039	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 53	open	Open	90.000	Mirror	contK	19:54:17 19:56:29	1.24-1.24	Focusing on Venus Filename: img
2040-2114	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 75	open	Open	90.000	Mirror	contK	19:58:15 20:01:23	1.25-1.25	Venus Quick Image Set Filename: img
2115-2139	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 25	open	Open	90.000	Mirror	Bry	20:01:37 20:02:38	1.25-1.25	Venus Quick Image Set Filename: img
2140-2214	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 75	open	PK_50	90.000	Mirror	1.74	20:03:06 20:06:14	1.25-1.25	Venus Quick Image Set Filename: img
2215-2239	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 25	open	PK_50	90.000	Mirror	Fell	20:06:54 20:07:55	1.25-1.25	Venus Quick Image Set Filename: img
2240-2249	Venus (299)	19.984	1 10	open	Open	90.000	Mirror	CO+ND2	20:08:19 20:11:56	1.25-1.26	Venus Quick Image Set Filename: img
2250-2269	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 20	open	Blank	90.000	Mirror	CO+ND2	20:12:37 20:13:25	1.26-1.26	Venus Quick Image Set Filename: dark_0241s_bias
2270-2274	Venus (299)	19.984	1 5	open	Open	90.000	Mirror	CO+ND2	20:13:37 20:15:14	1.26-1.26	Sky Quick Image Set (100 arcsec N) Filename: flat_CO
2275-2284	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 10	open	Open	90.000	Mirror	Fell	20:16:03 20:16:25	1.26-1.26	Sky Quick Image Set (100 arcsec N) Filename: flat_Fell
2285-2299	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 15	open	PK_50	90.000	Mirror	1.74	20:17:01 20:17:37	1.26-1.26	Sky Quick Image Set (100 arcsec N) Filename: flat_174
2300-2314	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 15	open	Open	90.000	Mirror	Bry	20:18:08 20:18:44	1.26-1.27	Sky Quick Image Set (100 arcsec N) Filename: flat_Bry
2315-2324	Venus (299)	0.2408	1 10	open	Open	90.000	Mirror	contK	20:18:54 20:19:17	1.27-1.27	Sky Quick Image Set (100 arcsec N) Filename: flat_contK
2325-2497	Venus (299)	0.1204	1 173	0.9	Long4	90.000	Mirror	5.1	20:21:36 20:31:54	1.27-1.29	Venus 5.1 Instant Sky Filename: img

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Frame #'s	Object	Expos (s)	Coadds	Dichr	OS Filter	PA (°)	Slit (")	Spect Mode	UT	HA Airmass	Comments
			Cycles						LST		
0001	Argon off	1.8534	15 1	open	Open	90.000	0.5x15	LXD_long	17:16:06	1.52	wavelength cal Filename: arc
0002	Argon on	1.8534	15 1	open	Open	90.000	0.5x15	LXD_long	17:16:56	1.51	wavelength cal Filename: arc
0003-0007	QTH	1.8534	2 5	open	0.1xSTOP	90.000	0.5x15	LXD_long	17:19:28 17:19:57	1.50-1.50	Flat Filename: flat
0008-0062	Venus (299)	0.4634	8 55	open	Open	90.000	0.5x15	LXD_long	17:22:38 17:34:06	1.49-1.44	Venus Night LXD_long Scan 1 Filename: spec
0063-0072	Venus (299)	0.4634	8 10	open	Open	90.000	0.5x15	LXD_long	17:36:13 17:38:08	1.43-1.42	Venus Night LXD_long Scan 1 (sky) Filename: spec
0073-0147	Venus (299)	0.4634	1 75	open	Open	90.000	0.5x15	LXD_long	17:41:18 17:44:51	1.41-1.40	Venus Day LXD_long Scan 1 Filename: spec
0148-0157	Venus (299)	0.4634	1 10	open	Open	90.000	0.5x15	LXD_long	17:45:56 17:46:22	1.39-1.39	Venus Day LXD_long Scan 1 (sky) Filename: spec
0158-0217	Venus (299)	0.4634	2 60	open	Open	90.000	0.5x60	Prism	17:50:05 17:54:36	1.38-1.37	Venus PRISM Scan 1 Filename: spec
0218-0227	Venus (299)	0.4634	2 10	open	Open	90.000	0.5x60	Prism	17:55:31 17:56:11	1.36-1.36	Venus PRISM Scan 1 (sky) Filename: spec
0228-0232	Inc lamp	0.9267	7 5	open	Open	90.000	0.5x60	Prism	17:57:20 17:58:32	1.36-1.36	Flat Filename: flat
0233	Argon lamp	0.4634	10 1	open	Open	90.000	0.5x60	Prism	17:59:02	1.35	wavelength cal Filename: arc
0234-0253	HD_177120	0.4634	4 20	open	Open	90.000	0.5x60	Prism	18:06:00 18:09:08	1.36-1.36	Reference Star with PRISM Filename: star_0464s
0254-0273	HD_177120	0.4634	4 20	open	Open	90.000	0.5x15	LXD_long	18:13:26 18:16:33	1.36-1.36	Reference Star with LXD_long Filename: star_0464s
0274-0281	HD_177120	1.8534	4 8	open	Open	90.000	0.5x15	LXD_long	18:16:41 18:19:10	1.36-1.36	Reference Star with LXD_long Filename: star_2s
0282-0351	Venus (299)	0.4634	2 70	open	Open	90.000	0.5x60	Prism	19:21:25 19:26:44	1.24-1.24	Venus PRISM Scan 2 Filename: spec
0352-0361	Venus (299)	0.4634	2 10	open	Open	90.000	0.5x60	Prism	19:27:00 19:27:41	1.24-1.24	Venus PRISM Scan 2 (sky) Filename: spec
0362-0366	Inc lamp	0.9267	7 5	open	Open	90.000	0.5x60	Prism	19:28:24 19:29:36	1.24-1.24	Flat Filename: flat
0367	Argon lamp	0.4634	10 1	open	Open	90.000	0.5x60	Prism	19:30:06	1.24	wavelength cal Filename: arc
0368-0372	Venus (299)	0.4634	8 5	open	Open	90.000	0.5x15	LXD_long	19:32:12 19:33:03	1.24-1.24	Venus Night LXD_long Scan 2 (sky) Filename: spec
0373-0428	Venus (299)	0.4634	8 56	open	Open	90.000	0.5x15	LXD_long	19:34:39 19:46:50	1.24-1.24	Venus Night LXD_long Scan 2 Filename: spec

